

NOVEL HIGH PERFORMANCE PHENOLIC MOULDING COMPOUNDS FOR INJECTION MOULDING

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SYNOPSIS

The mechanical properties of injection moulded short glass fibre reinforced phenolic composites are quite poor. The causes, among others, are the very short fibre length in the mouldings and the poor failure strength and strain of the phenolic resin itself. In order to improve the fibre length in the injection mouldings, a new compounding technique was developed based on pultrusion-impregnation. The initial fibre length in this compound is quite long (≈ 12.7 mm), which will result in a longer average fibre length in the mouldings. Details of this technique are presented. Significant improvement in mechanical performance of injection mouldings from this moulding compound was obtained because of the presence of longer fibres. Improvement to the failure strength and strain of the phenolic resin with the addition of an epoxy pre-preg resulted in further improvement in mechanical performance. The reasons for these improvements are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

There have been several major fire related disasters over the last few years, such as the fires in a passenger aircraft at the Manchester Airport, at the King's Cross station on the London Underground, on the Piper Alpha oil platform in the North Sea, and in the Bradford Football Stadium. These have resulted in tougher legislation requiring the use of fire resistant materials in public transportation systems and other engineering structures. Phenolic resin is one of the oldest synthetic polymers which with its intrinsic fire resistance, low smoke and toxic fume emission [1] makes it an ideal candidate for these structures. This has prompted more interest in the development of high-performance phenolic composites for engineering applications.

Injection moulding of phenolic composites, compared to compression moulding, has the advantages of high productivity, consistent product quality, and easy automation at the expense of mechanical performance. The mechanical performance of short glass fibre reinforced phenolic composites is very dependent on the length of fibre reinforcement, as well as the failure strength and strain of the phenolic matrix. This is demonstrated below [2]:

$$\sigma_{cu} = \sigma_{mu}(1 - V_f) + \sigma_f V_f \left(1 - \frac{l_c}{2l}\right) \quad (1)$$

for $l \geq l_c$

and

$$\sigma_{cu} = \sigma_{mu}(1 - V_f) + \sigma_f V_f \left(\frac{l}{2l_c}\right) \quad (2)$$

for $l < l_c$

where σ_{cu} is the tensile strength of the composite, l the fibre length whose critical fibre length is l_c , V_f the fibre volume fraction, σ_{mu} the ultimate tensile strength of the phenolic matrix and σ_f the stress in the fibre at the failure strain of the composite.

The traditional compounding method for phenolic moulding granules involves a two-roll mill [3]. It mixes phenolic resin with other ingredients, and advances the cure of the resin. The milled compound is then cooled down and granulated. For glass fibre reinforced phenolic moulding compound, the glass fibres have to be chopped to short length before mixing with the resin. The fibre length is further reduced during the milling and granulation processes. So the glass fibre length in a commercial phenolic moulding compound is usually very short, typically less than 0.25 mm [4]. High strength is very difficult to achieve with this short fibre reinforcement. Another disadvantage of phenolic composites is the low failure strain of matrix (<1%) [5], much lower than that of thermoplastics, which causes premature failure of the composites. The reinforcing efficiency of the glass fibre is not fully utilised before the composite fails.

Longer fibres and improved failure strength and strain of the phenolic resin will both improve the mechanical performance of short fibre reinforced phenolic composites. Based on the observation that a longer fibre length in the moulding compounds will result in longer fibre length in the injection mouldings [6,7] under similar injection moulding conditions, it is possible to increase the length of glass fibres in the mouldings by starting with a compound containing longer fibres. To improve the failure strength and strain of the phenolic resin, it is possible to modify the phenolic resin compound with other compounds of higher failure strength and strain. This paper presents a study of these two aspects.

EXPERIMENTAL

A pultrusion-impregnation set-up was designed and built. It is shown in Fig. 1. The set-up consists of three parts: fibre-impregnation unit, pultrusion unit and haul-off unit.

Figure 1. The pultrusion-impregnation set-up

The fibre-impregnation unit includes fibre guides, resin solution tank, and optional metering device. The main purpose of this unit is to impregnate the glass fibres with resin solution. The pultrusion unit consists of three dies in a row, each of 75 mm in length, and there is a 20 mm space between the dies. They are heated by band-heaters. The temperature of the dies is controlled by a temperature controller, and the thermocouple is installed on the middle die. The band-heaters can be switched off and on individually. A belt haul-off unit was used as the final stage of the pultrusion-impregnation process. It is driven by a DC motor with a Parvalux thyristor DC controller so that the speed can be adjusted easily.

Phenolic resin CS366 (TBA Composites Ltd) was dissolved in industrial methylated spirit (IMS) to form a solution with 65% solids, which was used to coat 1200 tex Silenka 084-M-19 glass fibre (Silenka bv, Netherlands) using the pultrusion-impregnation process. The die temperatures were set at 125°C, and the haul-off speed was ≈ 30 metres per hour.

The degree of cure of the phenolic resin within the pultrusion-impregnated glass fibre roving can be advanced in an oven at 110°C for 10 minutes before cutting. They were cut into pellets of 12.7 mm long with the glass fibre chopper for injection moulding.

The glass fibre - epoxy pre-preg, Fibredux-913G-E-39 (Ciba-Geigy Ltd), consists of E-glass fibre in the 913 epoxy resin containing micronised dicyandiamide as the curing agent. The fibre volume fraction of this pre-preg is about 55%. It was torn into tows manually and chopped into the same length as the chopped pultrusion-impregnated fibre roving, and mixed with them before injection moulding.

The injection moulding machine used was a BOY 22S Dipronic thermoset injection moulding machine with a thermoset screw of 24 mm in diameter. The injection moulding machine was equipped with a controlled clamp-breathing device so that during moulding any volatiles generated could be released. The mould used was long and thin with dimensions of 105 mm long by 2.8 mm wide by 2.7 mm thick (unidirectional mould). The mould temperature was set at 165°C, the barrel temperature at 75°C, the screw rotation speed at 70 rpm and the curing time at 70 seconds.

The moulded coupons were polished and their mechanical properties determined by flexural, tensile and interlaminar shear tests. The machine used was a MAYES SM200 universal testing machine. The span for the flexural test was 40 mm, and the deflection was measured with a transducer. The span for interlaminar shear test was 11.75 mm. All of the tests were carried out at a constant rate of cross-head displacement of 0.5 mm/minute.

For fibre volume fraction determination and fibre length measurement, the injection mouldings were weighed and then ashed at 600°C for at least 6 hours. The remnant was glass fibre only. It was weighed, and knowing the densities of glass fibre and phenolic resin, the fibre volume fraction could be determined. The fibre length in the remnant was analysed using an optical microscope fitted with an automatic image analyser. At least 800 fibres were measured to achieve a good representation of the fibre lengths present in the injection mouldings. Two types of averages were calculated; the number average fibre length \bar{l}_n and the weight average fibre length \bar{l}_w using the expressions given below:

$$\bar{l}_n = \frac{\sum_0^N N_i l_i}{\sum_0^N N_i} \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{l}_w = \frac{\sum_0^N N_i l_i^2}{\sum_0^N N_i l_i} \quad (4)$$

Where N_i is the number of fibres with the fibre length l_i , and N the total number of fibres measured.

For comparison purposes, a commercial phenolic moulding compound Perstorp A2630 (Perstorp Ferguson Ltd) was used. It is a short glass fibre filled moulding compound with 49% by weight of glass fibres and other mineral fillers. The mechanical properties and fibre length distribution of the injection mouldings from this moulding compound were also characterised.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CHARACTERISATION OF THE PULTRUSION-IMPREGNATED GLASS FIBRE - PHENOLIC RESIN MOULDING COMPOUND

Pultrusion-impregnation glass fibre with the phenolic resin was carried out with the pultrusion-impregnation set-up. It was found that the fibre volume fraction of pultrusion-impregnated glass fibre roving can be controlled by changing either the diameter of the die or the fibre roving tex. An example of the effect of changing fibre tex on the fibre volume fraction is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The fibre volume fraction of pultrusion-impregnated glass fibre roving with different fibre roving tex

Fibre tex	Fibre volume fraction (%)
600	29.7
1200	37.8
2400	49.5

In order to study the degree of resin impregnation during the fibre pultrusion process, the cross-sections of pultrusion-impregnated fibres were examined. A typical optical micrograph is shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the resin has efficiently impregnated the glass fibres.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Without Advancing the Cure of the Phenolic Resin

The injection moulding of pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets of 12.7 mm length was carried out without further advancing the cure of the phenolic resin after the pultrusion-impregnation process. The injection mouldings were 2.7 x 2.8 x 105 mm in dimension and the fibre volume fraction was 37.1%.

Flexural and interlaminar shear strength tests of these injection moulded samples were carried out. A total of nine specimens were tested for flexural properties and twelve specimens for interlaminar shear strength. The results are shown in Table 2. It can be seen that even without

advancing the degree of cure of the phenolic resin, the mechanical properties are better than those from the commercial moulding compound.

Figure 2. An optical micrograph showing the cross-section of a pultrusion-impregnated glass fibre roving (the average fibre diameter = 14.7 μ m).

Table 2. Mechanical performance of injection mouldings from pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets ($V_f=37.1\%$) in comparison with that from commercial moulding compound (Standard deviation in brackets)

Moulding compound	Pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets	Perstorp A2630
Flexural strength (MPa)	133.7 (19.4)	106.5 (8.5)
Flexural modulus (GPa)	14.8 (1.6)	12.4 (1.6)
Tensile strength (MPa)	—	56.1 (4.6)
Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	21.1 (2.2)	16.2 (0.9)

The injection mouldings manufactured from the pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets were ashed in a furnace at 600°C for 6 hours. The fibre length was determined using an image analyser. A total of 800 fibres were recorded. The results of the fibre length measurement are shown in Table 3. It can be seen from Table 3 that the average fibre length in the mouldings from the pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets is much larger than that from the commercial moulding compound. It can also be seen that the initial fibre length in the moulding is important; the longer the fibres in the compound, the longer the fibres in the mouldings. Table 3 shows that the damage to the fibre length during the injection moulding process is very severe.

With Advancing the Cure of the Phenolic Resin

Pultrusion-impregnated fibre rovings were placed in an oven at 110°C for 10 minutes, so as to further advance the cure of the phenolic resin before injection moulding. The resulting pellets were then injection moulded, and flexural and interlaminar shear strength tests carried out. The

flexural properties are the average from six specimens and the interlaminar shear strength is the average from ten specimens. The results are shown in Table 4.

Table 3. Comparison of the fibre length distribution in the injection moulding compounds and the injection mouldings.

Moulding compounds	Pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets	Perstorp A2630
<i>Fibre length in compound:</i>		
Number average fibre length (mm)	12.70	0.19
Weight average fibre length (mm)	12.70	0.41
<i>Fibre length in mouldings:</i>		
Number average fibre length (mm)	0.82	0.13
Weight average fibre length (mm)	1.56	0.18
Longest fibre (mm)	9.45	0.71
shortest fibre (mm)	0.15	0.01

Table 4. Mechanical performance of injection moulded pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets (Cure advanced at 110°C for 10 minutes) ($V_f=39.1\%$) (Standard deviation in brackets)

Flexural strength (MPa)	190.5 (19.0)
Flexural modulus (GPa)	17.0 (0.5)
Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	27.3 (3.7)

The above experiment was repeated to check the reproducibility of the results. All of the processing parameters were kept the same. The mechanical properties, including the tensile properties, of the injection mouldings are shown in Table 5 (9 specimens were tested for flexural properties, 8 for tensile properties and 5 for interlaminar shear properties). The fibre volume fraction was 38.7%.

Table 5. Mechanical performance of injection moulded pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets (Cure advanced at 110°C for 10 minutes) ($V_f=38.7\%$) (Standard deviation in brackets)

Flexural strength (MPa)	187.1 (21.0)
Flexural modulus (GPa)	16.1 (0.6)
Flexural failure strain (%)	1.26 (0.1)
Tensile strength (MPa)	81.3 (7.9)
Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	27.4 (3.0)

Comparing Tables 4 and 5, it can be seen that excellent reproducibility was achieved. It can also be seen that much better mechanical performance was obtained by injection moulding of pultrusion-impregnated glass fibre pellets, compared with mouldings from commercial moulding compound (Table 2). The improvement in mechanical performance is mainly due to the increase in fibre length retention in the mouldings. Comparing Tables 4 and 5 with Table 2, it can be seen that the mechanical properties of the injection mouldings were greatly improved by advancing the cure of the phenolic resin, this is mainly due to the improved mechanical strength of the phenolic matrix with the optimisation of the cure.

EPOXY MODIFICATION OF PHENOLIC MOULDING COMPOUND

Epoxy resins, in general, have better failure strengths and strains than the phenolic resin. They can also form a relatively strong interface with the glass fibre. So the addition of an epoxy resin pre-preg to the phenolic matrix composite has been studied. Epoxy pre-preg 913 was cut into the same length as the pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets (12.7 mm). 54.3 g of epoxy pre-preg was mixed with 142.0 g of pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets (27.7% of pre-preg by weight) and then injection moulded. The degree of cure of the phenolic resin in the pultrusion-impregnated fibres was not further advanced after the pultrusion-impregnation process. The fibre volume fraction of the injection mouldings was 39.6%.

Flexural and Interlaminar shear strength tests were carried out. A total of ten specimens were tested for each test and the results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Mechanical performance of injection moulded pultrusion-impregnated fibre pellets containing 27.7% epoxy pre-preg ($V_f=39.6\%$) (Standard deviation in brackets)

Flexural strength (MPa)	225.0 (21.9)
Flexural modulus (GPa)	17.1 (0.6)
Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	30.0 (2.5)

The flexural strength and the interlaminar shear strength of the injection mouldings modified with the epoxy pre-preg were much higher than those without pre-preg, and are much higher than those from the commercial moulding compound (Table 2). This is probably because of (a) a higher matrix strength; (b) improvement in the interfacial strength between the glass fibre and the matrix and (c) the interaction of phenolic and epoxy resins during the curing reaction. Further study has shown that the main contributing factors are the improvement in the failure strength and strain of the matrix [8].

CONCLUSIONS

A new phenolic compounding method employing pultrusion-impregnation has been developed. The fibre volume fraction can be controlled. The fibre length in the injection mouldings is significantly larger than that from the commercial moulding compound.

The significant improvements in the mechanical performance of the mouldings obtained from the pultrusion-impregnated phenolic moulding compound can be attributed to the increase in fibre length retention in the moulding.

Modification of phenolic moulding compound with an epoxy resin pre-preg resulted in further improvement in the mechanical performance. It has been shown [8] that this improvement is mainly a result of an increased failure strength and strain of the matrix.

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